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FORMULATION OF THE OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM FOR MANAGING WATER DISTRIBUTION IN CLOSED-TYPE IRRIGATION SYSTEMS

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***Abstract.** Interest in the management of irrigation in closed irrigation systems has significantly increased since the mid-20th century. This trend is closely related to the development of agriculture, the growing demand for irrigation, and technological advancements, which have led to the emergence of new methods and tools aimed at optimizing these systems. The necessity to consider agrotechnical measures, plant water requirements, and the technical parameters of irrigation systems in irrigation management requires the development of information and control systems focused on efficient water resource allocation and yield enhancement [1]. This article analyzes general approaches to the organization of irrigation in large closed irrigation systems. Different levels of irrigation system management are considered. To ensure effective management of such systems, information and control systems are being developed that take into account soil moisture, plant growth stages, agro-climatic data, and the technical characteristics of the irrigation network.*

***Keywords:** Land reclamation; optimization of irrigation processes; water distribution; operational management of irrigation.*

Introduction

The issue of managing closed irrigation systems has been actively discussed worldwide since the mid-20th century. During this period, alongside the widespread development of agriculture, the demand for irrigation sharply increased. This was driven by rapid population growth, the need to ensure food security, and the necessity to enhance the productivity of agricultural crops. Starting from the 1960s, as a result of intensified scientific research in hydraulic engineering and agriculture, theoretical

and practical foundations for managing hydro-meliorative systems began to take shape. During this time, significant attention was paid to studying effective methods of water resource distribution, developing automated irrigation systems, and creating models and decision-support systems aimed at optimizing the performance of irrigation systems [2].

One of the important milestones in the management of irrigation systems was the adoption and implementation of large-scale international projects in this field. Notably, the establishment of the International Commission on Irrigation and Drainage (ICID) on June 24, 1950, stands out as a significant achievement. Through these projects and initiatives, experience exchange between various countries, the introduction of advanced technologies, and the widespread application of modern approaches to irrigation system management began.

The necessity of managing irrigation systems under conditions of resource scarcity is being scientifically substantiated. Two different approaches have been proposed for defining objective functions to implement irrigation plans [3]. In conclusion, it is emphasized that the proposed management approach ensures adaptation to changes in soil moisture, weather conditions, and the planning of agrotechnical activities, which contributes to the efficient use of water resources and the creation of favorable conditions for plant growth. The optimization objective functions are aimed at bringing soil moisture close to an optimal level, which, in some periods, includes agrotechnical activities without irrigation. The integration of modern management methods and models enables a rapid response to changes in agro-meliorative and meteorological conditions, optimizes water resource distribution, and improves the accuracy of agrotechnical operations.

Materials and Methods

This study provides an in-depth analysis of modern approaches to organizing irrigation in large closed irrigation systems. A comprehensive approach to optimizing irrigation management is applied, encompassing all stages from data collection and analysis to conducting experimental trials and evaluating their effectiveness.

Research Results

To improve the current situation, it is essential to closely link water supply with crop areas and productivity. This approach is relevant not only at the central levels of irrigation systems (basin, regional, and district scales) but also within farm-level systems. One of the significant works in this field is the monograph by E. P. Galyamin, which identifies two main tasks in irrigation management: first, planning and distributing irrigation norms across crop areas; second, managing the execution

mechanisms of the irrigation network. Galyamin's research emphasizes that effective irrigation management should be based on crop conditions, soil properties, weather conditions, optimal soil moisture, and the technical parameters of the irrigation system. The operational management system of closed irrigation systems (CIS) is complex, encompassing water intake points, main canals, pumping stations, distribution canal networks, irrigated fields, and drip irrigation equipment [4]. Considering the numerous components of irrigation systems, planning water distribution and irrigation activities becomes a complex challenge. Factors such as changing weather conditions, the status of technical equipment, and resource availability influence this process. The interaction of these factors within the system is also of significant importance. In this regard, to improve the efficiency of closed irrigation systems, information-management systems are being developed that take into account soil moisture, plant growth stages, agro-climatic data, and technical characteristics of the irrigation network [5]. In conclusion, managing irrigation under conditions of resource scarcity is a pressing issue that requires deeper research and practical solutions. To enhance the efficiency of managing closed irrigation systems, information-management systems are being developed that consider soil moisture, the growth stages of plants, agro-meteorological data, and the technical characteristics of the system. In this way, managing irrigation under limited resource conditions becomes a critical task, necessitating further research and development in this field. Discrepancies in the calculation and implementation of irrigation regimes reduce the efficiency of agricultural crop management on irrigated lands. To address this problem, semi-automated irrigation planning systems have been introduced; however, their general recommendations do not always fully consider actual conditions [6]. When selecting the objective function for irrigation, two approaches should be distinguished. The first approach is technical-economic, while the second is technological, which is based solely on maintaining soil moisture at a specified level by considering the recommendations of the agronomic service of the farming enterprise. Each approach should be considered separately, even though many criteria and factors influencing the objective function may be similar.

In the first approach, the objective function of irrigation management is a mathematical expression related to the total yield and its value in the fields, aiming to maximize the economic benefit obtained from irrigation. This function takes into account not only the physical volume of the product obtained through irrigation but also price indicators related to the product itself and the costs of irrigation. The objective function can be represented in the following form:

$$\max F = \sum_{i=1}^n (P_i Y_i) - C_o - C_w, \quad (1)$$

Here F – Objective function (total economic benefit from irrigation); i – Index indicating the specific crop; n – Number of crops in the irrigated area; P_i – Price of one unit of the i -th crop; Y_i – Yield per unit area of the i -th crop due to irrigation; C_o – Total costs for irrigation (equipment depreciation, energy consumption, maintenance, etc.); C_w – Water expenses (water delivery, distribution, and use of water resources).

The purpose of this function is to determine the maximization of net profit from the yield by optimal distribution of water resources and irrigation management, taking into account the cost of water and irrigation expenses. This includes calculating the optimal water volume for each crop, the best timing for irrigation, and other parameters affecting productivity and economic efficiency. The task of forming an operational irrigation schedule for closed irrigation systems is viewed as an optimization problem with defined characteristics. A closed-type irrigation system includes a pumping station, a network of distribution pipes, and numerous fields S_j each with a specific area, occupied by agricultural crops (k) distributed across many j plots. Each j plot is irrigated by sprinklers, where n_j represents the set of machines assigned to the plot, and n denotes the serial number of a machine within the farm's irrigation system [7].

A field is an irrigated area that is uniform in terms of plant cover composition and is served by a certain number of sprinklers. From a technological process perspective, the irrigated field is divided into elementary parts, since each part is irrigated by only one specific sprinkler γ [8]. The j field of such an area, occupied by the k crop with a S_{jk} area and consisting of n elementary parts, as well as the area dependent on the number of machines servicing this field, is designated as follows:

$$\sum_{\gamma=1}^n \Delta S_{jk}^{\gamma} = S_{jk}, \quad (2)$$

Here, S_{jk} is the area of the j -field occupied by the k crop, n is the number of elementary parts and the number of machines.

The task of operational irrigation management includes the results of calculating irrigation regimes for each field, indicating the irrigation volume and timing. It is assumed that irrigation can be carried out within one day, without any technical parameter constraints. Operational management is usually coordinated with irrigation regime planning, typically carried out for periods of 10–14 days. This allows for the creation of an irrigation schedule for the irrigated fields [9]. The irrigation equipment management system must set optimal operating parameters (pressure, flow rate, duration, speed, etc.) while considering many factors. The primary goal of such a system is the optimal implementation of the calculated irrigation regime. In production conditions, changes in irrigation schedules may arise due to technical

constraints, which do not take into account the limitations of the irrigation network and equipment, even though theoretically it is possible to carry out irrigation in a short time. Based on the objective function of the optimization task presented above, the impact of delays in the scheduled irrigation date on the total yield value of the field is evaluated using the following formula:

$$u_j = k_k Y_{jk} Z_k s_j (t) |t^* - t|, \quad (3)$$

Here, u_j is the damage indicator caused by the delay in the irrigation date of the k -crop in the j -field for the s_j area; k_k is the proportionality coefficient; Y_{jk} is the planned yield of the k -crop in the j -field; Z_k is the price per unit of the k -crop; t^* is the planned irrigation date; t is the actual date of irrigation for the s_j area.

Conclusion

The proposed approach ensures flexibility in irrigation management, allowing adaptation not only to changes in soil moisture and weather conditions but also to the planning and execution of agro-technical measures in the fields. In this way, the developed model serves to optimize the use of water resources, minimize risks for plants, and improve favorable conditions for their growth and development. The proposed objective functions enable the optimization of irrigation management such that the current soil moisture is maximally close to the optimal level, irrigation costs are minimized, and conditions for plant growth are improved through the integrated implementation of agro-technical measures. Solving this problem requires complex optimization algorithms and decision-making models that consider a large number of variables and their interrelationships, including weather conditions, soil status, and the specific requirements of agricultural crops.

To integrate constraints related to agro-technical measures into the 7-day forecast-based irrigation management model, the model must take into account the start and end dates of these measures for each field. This ensures that irrigation is not carried out during periods when it is impossible due to agro-technical activities. The use of operational irrigation management tools in closed irrigation systems further refines the execution of agro-meliorative tasks, enables efficient use of technical resources, and ensures control over the network. This creates the ability to respond promptly to changes in weather, agro-technological, and farm conditions. The model system allows determining the optimal technological irrigation regime, water supply plans, and other parameters under specified conditions. This makes the water distribution and irrigation management process easier and more substantiated, ensuring the rational use of water resources.

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